

KURASHCHILARNI UMUMIY VA MAXSUS JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIGI: KURASHCHINING MAXSUS CHIDAMLILIGI

Solaydinov Elmurod Shoroidinovich

Andijon davlat universiteti

Sport faoliyati turlari nazariyasi va metodikasi kafedrası

elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Sport trenirovkasi jismoniy tayyorgarlikni hamda texnik-taktik va psixologik tayyorgarlikni amaliy bo‘limlarini qamrab oladi. Malakali sportchilar uchun MJTning ahamiyati alohida yuqoridir. Sport natijasi kuch qobiliyatlarini har xil turlarini namoyon qilinishi bilan belgilangan holatlarda, MJTning asosiy bo‘g‘inlaridan biri sifatida – maxsus kuch tayyorgarligi shakllanadi. U sportning zamonaviy nazariyasida trenirovka jarayonining ajralmas qismi sifatida ko‘rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: jismoniy sifatlar, tezkorlik, kuch, chidamlilik, epchillik, egiluvchanlik.

ОБЩАЯ И СПЕЦИАЛЬНАЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА БОРЦОВ: СПЕЦИАЛЬНАЯ ВЫНОСЛИВОСТЬ БОРЦА

Солайдинов Эльмурод Шороидинович

Кафедра теории и методики спортивной деятельности

Андижанского государственного университета

E-mail: elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

Аннотация: Система спортивной тренировки представляет собой основной компонент подготовки спортсмена. Наряду со спортивными соревнованиями и дополнительными факторами, повышающими тренировочный эффект, она

обеспечивает необходимый прирост спортивных результатов. Спортивная тренировка охватывает физическую подготовку, а также практические разделы технической, тактической и психологической подготовки. Особенно велико значение СФП для квалифицированных спортсменов [71; 464с]. В случае, когда спортивный результат обусловлен проявлением различных видов силовых способностей, одним из основных звеньев СФП спортсмена становится специальная силовая подготовка. В современной теории спорта она рассматривается как неотъемлемая часть тренировочного процесса.

Ключевые слова: физические качества, скорость, сила, выносливость, ловкость, гибкость.

GENERAL AND SPECIAL PHYSICAL FITNESS OF WRESTLERS: SPECIAL ENDURANCE OF A WRESTLER

Solaydinov Elmurod Shoroidinovich

Department of theory and methodology of sports activities

Andijan state university

E-mail: elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

Annotation: Sports training includes practical sections of physical training and technical-tactical and psychological training. The importance of MJT is especially high for skilled athletes. In cases where the result of sports is determined by the manifestation of various types of strength abilities, special strength training is formed as one of the main links of MJT. It is considered as an integral part of the training process in the modern theory of sports.

Keywords: physical qualities, speed, strength, endurance, agility, flexibility.

In scientific and educational literature, starting from the 1950s and 1960s, the term "psychophysical qualities" has been replaced with the term "physical qualities." The

concept of "physical qualities" has been thoroughly developed in scientific works, and this term is examined as measurable physiological and biomechanical aspects of a person's movement capabilities. The main physical qualities include speed, strength, endurance, agility, flexibility, and the sense of balance. A natural question arises: Can the concept of "physical (motor) qualities" be considered part of the general theory of physical education? It seems not. When viewing physical education as a system of interconnected components that forms an integral whole, it can be concluded that physical exercise is an important factor in the development and enhancement of a holistic and multidimensional person, along with their physical and psychological capabilities.

The system of sports training is a fundamental component of an athlete's preparation. It ensures the necessary growth of sports results alongside training efficiency, competitions, and additional factors.

Sports training encompasses both physical preparation and practical sections of technical-tactical and psychological preparation. The significance of special physical training (SPT) is particularly high for qualified athletes. The sports result is determined by the manifestation of various types of strength abilities under specific conditions, with SPT forming one of the main components. It is viewed as an integral part of the training process in modern sports theory. Since special physical training aims to develop specific strength abilities, it is necessary to clarify the term "strength abilities." This term has several definitions. "Strength abilities" refer to the manifestation of a person during a specific physical activity, based on the concept of "strength." It also refers to the ability to overcome mechanical and biomechanical forces with muscle contractions, affect movements, and resist them, thereby ensuring effective impact despite resistance forces (weight, inertia, external environmental resistance, etc.).

Special physical training is directly related to the direct manifestation of strength abilities not only in athletic sports but also in many other sports, particularly in middle-distance running and weightlifting, as well as in individual combat sports, which are typical representatives of free wrestling. The exercises aimed at developing special

strength depend on the specific characteristics of competition exercises, classified by the nature of exercise stereotypes. Understanding the levels of movement construction and analyzing athletes' movement actions enables the formulation of principles for optimizing the biomechanical structure of exercises in the special strength domain.

The first principle states that in sports with highly stereotypical movements, the sensory structure of competition and special exercises must correspond; in sports with less stereotypical movements, the kinematic and dynamic structures of competition and special exercises should align; and in sports characterized by situational non-standard movements, the loading muscle groups during the performance of competition and special exercises should be matched, taking into account the individual composition of the movement action.

The second principle considers implementing special exercises with increased loads on the relevant muscle groups during the most significant phases of competition exercises.

In summary, the concept of "psychophysical qualities" should be seen as the development of a person's physical and spiritual (psychic) capabilities. In individual combat sports, significant attention is given to the psychological aspects of sports training through the application of various training tools. Indicators of the psychological preparation of teenagers engaged in wrestling and employing various training options during the training process have been examined.

The training sessions in the experimental group were developed based on the typological characteristics of muscle activity energy supply, while the control group practiced according to traditional schemes. Growth in psychological preparation indicators occurred in both groups, with notable increases in the experimental group: motivation to achieve goals rose by 29.17%; readiness for risk increased by 45.05%; motivation to avoid failure increased by 23.98%; psychological preparation state grew by 33.43%; personal anxiety rose by 17.23%; and situational anxiety by 15.07%. All changes in indicators were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

In the control group, there were increases in the examined indicators: respectively – by 2.58%; 6.80%; 7.87%; 8.94%; 7.30%; and 5.51%, but the significance level of these changes was not statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It is noteworthy that during the research period, situational and personal anxiety, readiness for risk, and motivation to avoid failure indicators in the experimental group of wrestlers decreased to optimal levels.

Currently, it has been determined that the general physical preparation of young wrestlers who began training in freestyle wrestling at ages 7-8 is sufficiently low. Practice shows that most newcomers have a pre-existing low level of general physical preparation. All of this indicates the necessity of developing effective methodologies to enhance the general physical preparation of young wrestlers, especially in the initial stages of their training process. Therefore, improving the effectiveness of general physical preparation in the early stages of freestyle wrestlers' training is undoubtedly a pressing issue.

References:

1. Denisenko, A.N. (2018). Physical and Technical Training of Wrestlers Based on the Integration of Training Means of Freestyle and National Wrestling Khuresh. Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, 13.00.04. St. Petersburg, 173 p.
2. Yeryomin, I.B. (2003). Bilateral Regulation of Technical-Tactical Actions of Wrestlers Considering Individual Features. Author's abstract of dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, 13.00.04. St. Petersburg State Academy of Physical Culture named after P.F. Lesgaft. pp. 23-24.
3. Bernstein, N.A. (1991). On Agility and Its Development. Moscow: Physical Culture and Sport, 288 p.
4. Zatsiorsky, V.M. (1966). Physical Qualities of an Athlete: Fundamentals of Theory and Methodology of Education. Moscow: Physical Culture and Sport, 199 p.
5. Manolaki, V.G. (1991). Pedagogical Control Over the Physical and Technical Preparation of Female Judokas. Kishinev.